

Does the January effect anomaly still exist at Indonesia Stock Exchange ?

Debi Yunita Dewi¹ and Perdana Wahyu Santosa²

¹Faculty of Economics and Business University of YARSI, Indonesia

²Program in Master of Management University of YARSI, Indonesia

Corresponding author: perdana.wahyu@yarsi.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine whether the January effect phenomenon occurred in the LQ45 Stock Index, IHSG and JII on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The January Effect phenomenon is one of the market anomalies, which states that stock returns in January tend to be higher compared to other months of the year. The January effect occurs because of tax-loss selling, window dressing, and stock's beta. The population of this research is the stock index in the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The research sample consisted of three selected using the complex probability sampling method with a systematic sampling design, namely the three leading indexes with a 6-year observation period. The results showed that the January effect phenomenon did not exist in the LQ45, IHSG, and JII stock indexes in the 2012-2017 period. Conclusion: the January effect does not exist at IDX with the lower magnitude of the anomaly effect, the efficiency of asset prices in the market is getting better because the market absorbs all information. In exchange perspective, daily trading volume intensity was getting lower in some recent years, especially in the two last week of January. This study has identified the effect of market microstructure, such as bid-ask spread and lower trading volume.

Keywords: return, stock, anomaly, January effect, CSPI, LQ45, JII, IDX

I. INTRODUCTION

The dynamics of financial markets have attracted the interest of researchers to conduct studies related to abnormal phenomena or better known as anomalies caused by market efficiency, financial behavior, and market microstructure for each different market. One interesting anomaly to study is the January Effect which stock return in January higher than others in the year. There have been many studies on the January Effect, especially on the Indonesia Stock Exchange with conclusions are still different from each study (Santosa and Santoso, 2019; Perez, 2018; Sari and Sisdyani, 2014; Wijaya et al. 2013; Wulandari, 2014).

The January effect, the observation that January seems to have a systematically higher return than other months of the year, is one of the most widely known of these anomalies on financial market globally. Some previous research has focused on the investors ability to take chance of the January effect using mutual funds or stock index (Moller and Zilca, 2008; Rendon and Ziemba, 2005). The sale of shares at the end of the year tends to increase to reduce tax (tax loss selling) that is borne, thus encouraging investors to realize "capital gains" in the current year, and the influence of "window dressing" in which the issuers "beautify" their financial statements so that stock prices increase and investors realize share profits for the Christmas and New Year holidays. Because of some of these causes the company will experience a shortage of funds for its operations at the beginning of the year, it causes the company to issue shares by offering high stock returns

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so that many investors will buy their shares and invest in the company so that the company can run its operations well in the beginning years (Jones, 2014; Kampman, 2012; Moller and Zilca, 2008).

The January effect is one step for a trader to determine the strategy for trading that year. For a 'long position' trader, the January effect is a crucial clue to determine the strategy by which they will execute the strategy to make profits. As for a 'short position' trader, the January effect is a prelude to making a decision not to enter the market during that period (Santosa and Santoso, 2019; Perez, 2018). Wulandari (2014) found that there is a January Effect. However, research conducted by Sari and Sisdyani (2014) on 82 companies obtained the results of data analysis which showed that there were no differences in stock returns in January with other than January in the Indonesian capital market, so the findings concluded that in the Indonesian capital market there was no January effect.

Maliasari (2013) concluded that the January effect occurred in the 2012 period affected abnormal returns. Research on the January Effect was also carried out in 2013 by Fitriyani and Sari on LQ45 stock index group on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the 2009-2011 period found that the January effect phenomenon occurred on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during that period.

This article aims to test whether the January Effect occurs or not on the Indonesia Stock Exchange through three main and leading indexes, namely the composite index, JCI, the blue chips index, LQ45, and islamic index, JII. Tests carried out in the period 2012-2017. The study also conducted a comprehensive test of the three leading indices and compared them to examine whether there were differences in the results of the three.

II. LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESIS

2.1 January Effect

The January effect is a market anomaly which states that stock returns in January tend to be higher than others in the year. According to Jones (2014), the January effect is caused by:

- a. Tax-loss selling.
Tax-loss selling is a phenomenon by selling shares with bad results in order to improve its financial statements, which will have an impact on tax reductions at the end of the year.
- b. Window Dressing.
Window Dressing is an activity to sell stocks with significant losses aimed at improving the company's year-end portfolio to make it look good.
- c. Stock's beta.
Stock's beta is a trend that occurs when, in January, smaller companies provide a higher rate of return compared to large companies.

According to Bodie et al. (2019), two causes of the January effect are:

"Tax-loss selling and window dressing leads to a conclusion that when the end of the year, circulating shares are stocks that have bad results, causing stock trading activities to decline. When stock trading activities have declined at the end of the year, to improve this, at the beginning of the year companies will tend to throw high-value stocks to provoke market reaction. These events will then cause a market reaction at the beginning of the year will tend to be higher, because investors believe that stocks thrown at the beginning of the year promise more guarantee results when compared to others. "

There are three theories agreed upon by traders that underlie the January Effect, namely:

"The first theory states that market movements that occurred in January are indicative of market movements in the year. A positive movement (where the stock price tends to increase) indicates a favorable year, while if there is a movement that tends to weaken, then indicates an unfavorable year. The second theory states that in the event of the January effect, third-tier stocks will tend not to reflect upper-tier stocks and shares that have experienced a strengthening in the previous year. The third theory is a variation of the second theory, which is stated in the January effect, the first five days in January can be a strong enough indication of the trade pattern of the year "(www.sirusindo.com).

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The January Effect is one of the market anomalies that states that stock returns offered by companies in January tend to be higher compared to others in the year. January Effect is also a phenomenon that occurs related to the change in years, namely December as the end of the tax year and January as the beginning of the tax year (Bodie et al. 2019; Santosa and Hosen, 2011). The January effect can also occur due to actions to create tax loss for investors. Usually, at the end of the year, many investment advisers advise investors to sell securities that suffer losses before the end of the year and, at the beginning of the year, buy the same securities (Bodie et al. 2019). If the amount of tax loss is substantial, it can be used to cover the transaction costs incurred. This stock selling at the end of December and buying at the beginning of January is creating the abnormal stock return or anomaly in the last two weeks of January (Kampman, 2012; Santosa and Santoso, 2019).

Branch (1977) and Reinganum (1983), found that purchases of declining securities in December will get abnormal returns in January. Branch analyzes the trading rule, which includes purchases of securities that experience low returns in the last week of December. Branch found that these securities in the first four weeks of the following year will experience price increases faster than the market as a whole, with very little risk difference. The January Effect phenomenon is statistically explained to occur because of a pattern that recurs almost every year. This pattern has caused many investors to take advantage of this pattern to develop strategies for making profits on the stock market. When a pattern is widely known, and many investors are simultaneously anticipating it, the pattern will disappear slowly. Although there has been a lot of information and research on the January Effect, the seasonal pattern is still happening today (Sihombing, 2011).

The January effect phenomenon also occurs in the US stock market. According to Wira (2015), the January Effect phenomenon in the American stock market is still quite useful, but after that, the effect began to be insignificant. This chance is likely many investors using investment plans that are protected by tax, so there is no need to sell shares at the end of the year. According to Haug and Hirschey (2006), the United States equity document shows that abnormal stock returns on small-cap stocks are very consistent at all times and do not appear to be affected.

Research conducted by Wijaya, et al. (2013) by analyzing the January effect on the manufacturing sector on the Indonesia Stock Exchange to find out whether there is a pattern of the January effect found that no pattern of the January effect occurred. The January effect study conducted by Wulandari (2014) on LQ45 shares found that the January effect occurred on LQ45 shares in the 2009-2013 period. Sari and Sisdyani (2014) analyzed the January effect using a sample of 82 companies listed on the Indonesian capitalmarket. From this research, the findings concluded that there was no January effect on the Indonesian Capital Market.

Maliasari (2013) conducted a study to find out the influence of the January effect on abnormal return in 2012. The research conducted showed that the January effect that existed in 2012 influenced abnormal return. According to Fitriyani and Sari (2013), the research conducted in 2013 by analyzing the occurrence of the January effect on the LQ45 stock index in the 2009-2011 period showed that the January effect phenomenon occurred on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

Using JII stock index research objects for the 2003-2008 period, As'adah (2009) study used the paired sample t-test method for testing and obtained a p-value of 0.939 so that it concluded that there was no January effect in the study. The January effect study conducted by Suseno (2012) in the mining sector in the 2003-2010 period using the One Way ANOVA test showed results that stated that there was no January effect in the study. Research on the January effect was also carried out by Pranoto (2007) using a sample of 43 issuers from the 1998-2005 period and using the multiple regression test model, and the results concluded that the January effect did not exist in the study.

According to research conducted by Haug and Hirschey (2006) on United States equity documents shows that abnormal returns on small-cap stocks are very consistent at all times and do not appear to be affected by the enactment of the Tax Reform Act of 1986. The research provides a new perspective for the tax-loss selling hypothesis and shows that the behavior is relevant to the January effect. Empirical research conducted by TijmenKampman from Tilburg University in 2012 using index data from the Standards and Poor 500 (S&P 500) between 1975 and 2000 proved that the January effect did not occur in the study period.

2.2 Hypothesis Formulation

With the results of research that contradict each other, this research takes into consideration whether there is a January effect phenomenon on the LQ45 Stock Index, IHSG, and JII. This study will propose a hypothesis to strengthen previous research on the presence or absence of the January effect to support or oppose the efficient market hypothesis by research using LQ45, JCI and JII stock index returns that were active in the 2012-2017 period with various events in it that caused the stock price to experience increase and decrease. The hypothesis for this study is obtained:

- a. H1: Returns on the LQ45 shares index that are actively listed have a difference between January and others, which indicates the January effect phenomenon.
- b. H2: return on active listed JCI has a difference between January and others which indicates the January effect phenomenon
- c. H3: Return on active listed JII stock index has a difference between January and others, which indicates the January effect phenomenon.
- d. H4: There is a significant January Effect difference on the LQ45, IHSG, and JII stock indexes.

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This type of research is Event Study research. According to Santosa and Hidayat (2014), an event study is an empirical analysis that studies the market reaction to an event that publish information as an event. In general, event studies are useful to find out whether a particular or a specific event triggers a stock price movement in the capital market. A stock price movement can usually be measured using stock returns.

3.1 Data Types and Sources

The type of data in this research is secondary data. Secondary data is primary data that has been processed in advance and has been presented by other parties. Data obtained from the Indonesia Stock Exchange website (www.idx.co.id) in the form of annual statistical reports and the Yahoo Finance website (www.finance.yahoo.com), which contains stock price information from each stock index contained in the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2010 to 2015.

3.2 Data collection technique

Data collection techniques used in this study are:

Literature study, which is by looking for literature related to this research, both from books, journals, theses, theses.

Data collection through internet media, namely by downloading annual statistical reports containing stock prices from the LQ45, IHSG and JII stock indexes for the 2012-2017 period through the Indonesia Stock Exchange website (www.idx.co.id) and the Yahoo Finance website (www.finance.yahoo.com).

3.3 Population and Sample

Population data is all data available and covered in a study that has specific characteristics. Generally, the population in the study is determined based on considerations that are appropriate to the type, motivation, and purpose of the study. In this study, the population is the stock index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Data Samples are part of the research population data that will be conducted which will represent the characteristics of the population determined. The sampling technique used is a complex probability sampling with a systematic sampling design, which is the three leading stock indexes: IHSG, LQ45 and JII.

3.5 Data Analysis

3.5.1 Descriptive Analysis Test

The descriptive analysis method in this study describes the various data collected to be selected, classified, processed in statistical hypothesis testing, and interpreted by concluding. This study collected data in the form of calculating stock returns from the LQ45, IHSG, and JII stock indexes for the 2012-2017 period.

3.5.2 Homogeneity Test

The homogeneity test determines whether several population variants are the same or not. This test as a prerequisite in the analysis of independent sample t-test and ANOVA. As a testing criterion, if the significance value is more than 0.05, it can be said that the variants of two or more groups of data are the same.

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3.5.3 Normality test

The normality test aims to test whether there is a normal distribution or not in the dependent variable and the independent variable. If in the Kolmogorov Smirnov test table, normality can be determined from the magnitude of significance. If the significance is > 0.05 , then the data is typically distributed and vice versa.

3.5.4 ANOVA test

ANOVA testing (F test) generated data in the normality test distributed normally. The ANOVA test aims to determine whether there is a significant difference between the average of more than two samples. The F test determines whether January returns differ significantly from other returns. The testing hypothesis is as follows:

H1: There is a January effect on the LQ45, IHSG and JII stock indexes for the 2012-2017 period.

Information:

- If $F_{table} < F_{count}$, at $\alpha = 5\%$, then H1 is accepted
- If $F_{table} > F_{count}$, at $\alpha = 5\%$, then H1 is rejected

3.5.5 Non-Parametric Test (Kruskall-Wallis)

When testing the normality of the data, the results of data distributed normally. Testing can be done with the Kruskal Wallis Non-Parametric test. This test compares the average of three or more samples so that it is an alternative to the analysis of variance for 1-way (ANOVA) or hypothesis testing of 3 or more average with 6 using the distribution for one direction of the parametric test. The criteria for testing with the Kruskal Wallis test are as follows:

- If $P\text{-value} < \alpha$, then H1 is accepted, $\alpha = 0.05$
- If $P\text{-value} > \alpha$ then H1 is rejected, $\alpha = 0.05$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis method in this study describes the various data collected to be selected, classified, processed in the testing of statistical hypotheses, and interpreted by concluding. Based on the results of descriptive statistical tests obtained by six observational data from the study period with a total sample of three indexes and two control variables, January and non-January.

Table 1 shows that the amount of data (N) used was 6 data from January and non-January stock returns 2012-2017 period that indicates that all data can be processed well and no missing data.

Table 1. Descriptive Analysis Results

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
LQ45	Januari	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6	100.0%
	Non Januari (mean Feb to Des)	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6	100.0%
IHSG	Januari	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6	100.0%
	Non Januari (mean Feb to Des)	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6	100.0%
JII	Januari	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6	100.0%
	Non Januari (mean Feb to Des)	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6	100.0%

4.2 Homogeneity Analysis

The homogeneity test is a test to determine whether several population variants are the same or not and is one of the prerequisites for conducting independent t-tests and ANOVA, which is used to find out whether some population variants are the same or not. Based on homogeneity test results in this study, both the

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LQ45, JCI, and JII have a significance value of more than 0.05, which means that all variants in this study are homogeneous and accept Ho. Following are the results of homogeneity tests on LQ45, IHSG, and JII:

4.2.1 LQ45 homogeneity test:

Sig value = 0.135 > 0.05 so that the Ho or data on the LQ45 stock index is homogeneous with data from other stock indexes.

4.2.2 IHSG homogeneity test:

Sig value = 0.180 > 0.05 so that it accepts Ho or data on the JCI stock index is homogeneous to data from other stock indexes.

4.2.3 JII homogeneity test:

Sig value = 0.103 > 0.05, so accepting Ho or data on the JII stock index is homogeneous with data from other stock indexes.

Tabel 2. Test of Homogeneity of Variance

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.	
LQ45	Based on Mean	2.649	1	10	.135
	Based on Median	.715	1	10	.418
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.715	1	5.236	.435
	Based on trimmed mean	1.799	1	10	.210
	Based on Mean	2.083	1	10	.180
IHSG	Based on Median	.386	1	10	.548
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.386	1	5.525	.559
	Based on trimmed mean	1.472	1	10	.253
	Based on Mean	3.222	1	10	.103
JII	Based on Median	.872	1	10	.372
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.872	1	5.192	.392
	Based on trimmed mean	2.285	1	10	.162

4.3 Normality Analysis

Normality analysis aims to test whether there is a normal distribution or not in the dependent variable and the independent variable. The normality test is also one of the prerequisites for conducting the ANOVA test. If the data is normally distributed and meets the requirements for conducting the ANOVA test, but if the data distributed not normally, then it will be continued with other tests, or in this study will be continued with the Kruskal-Wallis test. Based on the test results in this study, the following results:

4.3.1 LQ45 normality test:

January: Shapiro Wilk's Test Sig value = 0.003 < 0.05 so that he receives H1, that is, data distributed normally.

Non-January: Shapiro Wilk's Sig Test Value = 0.890 > 0.05 so that he receives HO, which is normally distributed data.

Result: The LQ45 normality test does not meet the normality assumption, so the ANOVA test was replaced with the Kruskal Wallis test.

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4.3.2 IHSG normality test:

January: Shapiro Wilk's Test Sig = 0.001 < 0.05 so that he receives H₁ (1), which is data that is not normally distributed. Non-January: Shapiro Wilk's Sig Test Value = 0.923 > 0.05 so that he receives H₀ ie the data is normally distributed.

Results: The CSPI normality test did not meet the normality assumption, so the ANOVA test was replaced with the Kruskal Wallis test.

Table 3. Tests of Normality

		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
LQ45	January	.385	6	.006	.675	6	.003
	Non January (mean Feb to Des)	.152	6	.200*	.970	6	.890
IHSG	January	.352	6	.020	.622	6	.001
	Non January (mean Feb to Des)	.177	6	.200*	.975	6	.923
JII	January	.406	6	.002	.679	6	.004
	Non January (mean Feb to Des)	.174	6	.200*	.974	6	.917

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

4.3.3 JII normality tes:

January: Shapiro Wilk's Test Sig value = 0.004 < 0.05 so that he receives H₁ which is data that is not normally distributed. Non-January: Shapiro Wilk's Sig Test Value = 0.917 > 0.05 so that he receives H₀ ie, data that is normally distributed.

Result: JII normality test does not meet the assumption of normality, so the Anova Test was replaced with the Kruskal Wallis test.

Based on the results obtained in the normality test for the data used in this study, it concluded that the data in this study distributed not normally (has a significance value < 0.05) so that the data does not meet the requirements for conducting ANOVA tests. As a substitute for the ANOVA test, the research continued using the Kruskal Wallis analysis test.

4.4 Kruskal Wallis Non-Parametric Analysis

Kruskal Wallis Non-Parametric analysis test is an alternative test from the ANOVA test because the normality test shows that the data used in this study are not normally distributed. Kruskal Wallis test compares the differences in stock returns in January and non-January stock returns by looking at the significance value obtained from testing.

If the significance value is less than 0.05, then the test can be concluded accepting H₁ and rejecting H₀ and vice versa; if the significance value is greater than 0.05, then the test can be concluded accepting H₀ and rejecting H₁. Based on the results generated from the Kruskal Wallis test, the following results obtained:

LQ45: Sig value 0.150 > 0.05 so that it receives H₀.

Result: There is no difference in LQ45 between January and non-January.

CSPI: Sig Value 0.262 > 0.05 so that it receives H₀.

Result: There was no difference in the JCI between January and non-January.

Table 4. Test Statistics^{a,b}

	LQ45	IHSG	JII
Chi-Square	2.077	1.256	3.103
Df	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	.150	.262	.078

a. Kruskal Wallis Test;

b. Grouping Variable:

JII: Sig Value 0.078 > 0.05 so that it receives Ho.

Result: There is no difference in JII between January and non-January.

The Kruskal Wallis test results concluded that both at LQ45, JCI, and JII obtained a significance value > 0.05, so there was no significant difference between January stock returns against non-January stock returns or January effect did not occur on the LQ45, IHSG stock index and JII in the period 2012-2017.

4.5 Discussion

In this study, using the Kruskal Wallis test model and the result is that there is no January effect on all stock indexes that are the object of research, namely LQ45, IHSG and JII in a period during 2012-2017. The results of the study indicate that the significance value of the test is higher than 0.05 on all major stock indices. In the LQ45 stock index obtained a significance value of 0.150, the IHSG obtained a significance value of 0.262 and on the JII stock index obtained a result of 0.078. Based on the test results that show a significance value higher than 0.05 so that this study accepts Ho and rejects H1.

Thus the hypothesis which states that there is a January effect on the LQ45 stock index, JCI, and JII, then the hypothesis is rejected or not proven, because the results obtained in this study are inversely proportional to the hypothesis previously estimated. Thus, the results of this study concluded that there is no January effect on the LQ45 stock index, IHSG and JII listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2012-2017. In previous studies, some results contradicted the hypotheses expected from research on the January effect by using research objects, research periods, and various test models. Moller and Zilca (2008) and Perez (2018) concluded that January effect is shorter duration of seasonal effect, generally. Although the abnormal return is lower in the second part of January, a higher abnormal return still occurs in the first part of January, making the effect of the January effect persists.

In addition to Indonesia, the January effect research proves that the January effect was not proven to occur in the study, one of which was an empirical study conducted by Kampman in 2012 using index data from the Standards and Poor 500 (S&P 500) between 1975 and 2000 proved that the January effect did not occur in the study period. Guler (2013) conducted January effect research in several countries, namely China, Argentina, Turkey, Brazil, and India. In that study, the January effect was found in 3 countries, namely China, Argentina, and Turkey, while in Brazil and India, the January effect has not existed. Perez (2018) explains that anomalous effects can still be existed in some markets; it decreases globally over time. It was also found that there appeared to be a January Reverse Effect in some markets with returns in January lower than returns in other months. This analysis was carried out with a nonparametric test.

V. CONCLUSION

On the LQ45 blue chips stock index, January stock returns are not significant to other non-January stock returns. So it was concluded that there was no January effect on the LQ45 stock index. Then on the JCI composite stock index, January stock returns are also not significant to stock returns in other non-January months, so it was concluded that there was no January effect on the JCI stock index. On the JII stock index, January stock returns are not significant to other stock returns. So it can be concluded that there was no January effect on the JII stock index. There was no significant difference in the January effect on the LQ45,

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JCI and JII stock indexes for the 2012-2017 period, therefore the anomaly January effect does not exist on the three leading stock indices LQ45, IHSG and JII at Indonesia Stock Exchange.

Despite strong empirical study for existence of January effect, some recent research has argued that the magnitude of this anomaly has declined continually. However in Indonesia Stock Exchange the magnitude of January effect is getting lower than before because of some reason such as subsequent research confirmed these findings that effect concentrated in the small firms. In exchange perspective, daily trading volume intensity was getting lower in some recent years, especially in the two last week of January. Other consideration have identified that effect of market microstructure such as bid-ask spread, low trading volume and explicit rules of the capital market.

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